

where, $|A|$ and $|g|$ are average A and g values, p is the free ion dipole term which is given a value of 0.036 cm^{-1} and K is the Fermi contact term which is actually given a value of 0.43.

To obtain in-plane and out-of-plane bonding parameters β^2 and γ^2 respectively, the following simplified expressions were used assuming tetragonal D_{4h} symmetry for Cu(II) in HMMCO and BPPTB complexes¹⁰.

$$g_{||} = 2.0023 - \frac{8\xi\alpha^2\beta^2}{\Delta E(B_{1g} \rightarrow B_{2g})} \quad \dots \text{ (II)}$$

$$g_{\perp} = 2.0023 - \frac{2\xi\alpha^2\beta^2}{\Delta E(B_{1g} \rightarrow E_g)} \quad \dots \text{ (III)}$$

The symbol ξ represents the one electron spin orbit coupling coefficient ($= -828 \text{ cm}^{-1}$).

The values of α^2 , β^2 and γ^2 are set out in Table 4. The bonding parameter α^2 is a measure

TABLE 4—BONDING PARAMETERS OF COPPER(II) COMPLEXES

Copper(II) complexes of	α^2	β^2	γ^2
HMMCO	0.68	0.70	0.68
BPPTB	0.71	0.66	0.51

of the covalency of the plane σ bonding. A value of $\alpha^2 = 1$ indicates complete ionic character while $\alpha^2 = 0.5$ indicates essentially 100% covalent bonding. The β^2 and γ^2 parameters are a measure for covalency in the in-plane and out-of-plane bonding, respectively. β^2 or $\gamma^2 = 1$ indicates no covalent bond and β^2 and $\gamma^2 = 0.5$ corresponds to total covalent character.

The observed value of α^2 , β^2 and γ^2 parameters in the present case are indicative of strong in-plane σ and π covalent bonding and out-of-plane π bonding. Out-of-plane covalency character is observed to be more in the BPPTB than in HMMCO complex which may be attributed to the presence of vacant d orbitals in sulphur atom of BPPTB. This favours back π bonding from metal to ligand.

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Stability Constants and Thermodynamic Parameters of Neodymium(III) Complexes with Mandelic, Cinnamic and Phenylacetic Acids: A Polarographic Study

FARID KHAN and A. V. MAHAJANI*

Department of Chemistry, University of Saugar,
Sagar-470 003, M. P.

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MANDELIC, cinnamic and phenylacetic acids were used as complexing agents for metals by different authors¹⁻³. A survey of literature shows that the complexation study of rare earth metal ions with these ligands have not been reported polarographically. In the present paper the authors report the stability constants and thermodynamic parameters of neodymium(III) complexes with mandelic, cinnamic and phenylacetic acid.

NOTES

TABLE I—METAL LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF THE COMPLEXES AT $\mu=1.0$ M POTASSIUM CHLORIDE

		Mandelic acid		Cinnamic acid		Phenylacetic acid	
		25°	35°	25°	35°	25°	35°
Metal ligand stability constant log K	Neodymium(III)	6.5	6.0	3.2	2.7	4.8	3.8
Change in enthalpy (ΔH) in K cal/mole	Neodymium(III)	-20.5		-17.7		-24.0	
Change in free energy (ΔG) in K cal/mole	Neodymium(III)	-8.9	-8.5	-4.3	-3.9	-5.9	-5.8
Change in entropy (ΔS) in cal/degree/mole	Neodymium(III)	-39.0	-40.0	-45.0	-45.0	-60.9	-66.6

Experimental

A.R. grade chemicals were used to prepare all the solutions. The metal solution was prepared by dissolving the calculated amount of metal oxide in minimum hydrochloric acid and was standardized with EDTA⁴. The solutions of ligands were prepared in double distilled water.

The concentration of metal ion, gelatine and potassium chloride in the test electrolytic solution was fixed at 2 mM, 0.01% and 1.0 M, respectively. The ligand concentration was varied from 1.0 mM to 10.0 mM. Ionic strength was fixed at $\mu=1.0$ with potassium chloride. An Ellico digital pH meter (Model L 1-120) was used to fix the pH of the test electrolytic solution at 2.4 ± 0.02 .

An automatic pen recording (C.I.C., Baroda, India) polarograph was used to record the polarograms. The capillary used had an 'm' value of 2.20 mg/sec and drop time of 3.1 sec/drop when measured in an air free 1.0 M potassium chloride at 46.0 cm effective height of the mercury column. Pure nitrogen was used for deoxygenating the solution before recording the polarograms. All the measurements were carried out at 25° and 35°, thermostatically controlled.

Results and Discussion

Nd(III) gives a well defined reversible three-electron reduction wave in 1.0 M potassium chloride + 0.01% gelatin at pH 2.75⁵⁻⁶. The reduction of Nd(III) and Nd(III)-complexes with all the three ligands were found to be of diffusion controlled nature as the plots of i vs $\sqrt{t}$ yield straight lines passing through the origin. An analysis of the

plots of E_{dms} vs $\log \frac{i}{i_d - i}$ and $E_{5/4} - E_{1/4}$ values for simple Nd(III) and its complexes with all the three ligands revealed the reversible nature of the reduction waves. The half wave potential of Nd(III) shifted to a more negative value on increasing the concentration of ligands. Lingane⁷ method was used

to find out the composition and stability constants of Nd(III) complexes with mandelic, cinnamic and phenylacetic acids. The thermodynamic parameters were calculated by the well known thermodynamic relations⁸. The composition, stability constants and thermodynamic parameters are given in Table I.

The stability constants of 1:1 complexes with respect to the ligands was found to be greater for phenylacetic acid than for cinnamic acid which is the order of their basicity. The unsaturated double bond present in cinnamic acid also contribute to lower stability⁸ to its metal complexes. Mandelic acid forms a chelate with the stoichiometry 1:2 giving maximum stability to its metal complex.

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